

Towards Cooperative ESS for Distribution Systems with high penetration of RES and EV

The Storage4Grid vision

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Abstract—Storage4Grid (S4G) is a 36-months project funded by the European Commission under the call LCE-01-2016, area 1 (Storage). S4G proposes an innovative holistic methodology for modelling, planning, integrating, operating and evaluating distributed Energy Storage Systems (ESS) including storage at user premises and storage at substation level, Electrical Vehicles (EV), innovative energy metering and energy routing technologies. This paper presents a systematic strategy used by S4G to generate the use cases for two scenarios related to two test sites: in Bolzano focused on cooperative EV charging and in Fur addressing the impact of user and grid side storage coordination to the medium and low voltage distribution network. The paper summarizes the S4G vision, solutions, and approaches for evolving the cooperative and coordinated ESS scenarios into use-cases and related requirements.

Keywords—ESS; Simulation; EV charging; Interfaces; Smart Grids; Smart Metering

I. INTRODUCTION

The European Commission has recently released a new Winter package [1] with the most recent updates on the European vision to deliver and share secure and clean energy among the member states. Energy Storage Systems (ESS) are emerging as one of the future trends for enabling renewable integration, energy efficiency, system resilience and other various smart grids applications.

ESS are long awaited components which can change the paradigm of needing all the time to produce equally as it is consumed. In the past, the production-consumption equilibrium was easier to be kept, since a significant share of energy was provided by controllable sources. However, the active networks of today need to support high penetration of renewables. Power grids have been in need for energy storage capabilities already for a long time, but due to cost reasons, such solutions have not yet been widely applied. Nevertheless, the storage technologies market is rapidly changing, due to the

increased maturity of ESS technology and the massive scale-up of production.

When having local production, e.g. through a rooftop PhotoVoltaic (PV), the local consumption of energy should be maximized as a response to reduction of feed-in tariff in many countries, and as grid parity for energy price has been reached already in some of them. Installing local storage at each prosumer is one possible solution, but as prosumers differ in consumption behaviour, averaging the storage need for a cluster of prosumers results in higher flexibility using less storage capacity in total than the sum of individual storage. Based on this fact, cooperative energy storage may be a more efficient solution. As a drawback, such choice calls for better correlation among production, consumption and storage, but features along this need are currently being delivered through evolving smart grid technologies. The two possible ESS placements, at prosumer level and on grid level, can be also combined in a smart cooperative storage.

Similarly, the charging of Electrical Vehicles (EV) can be implemented by better coordinating EV charging behaviours, but also by improving the coordination of available ESS which can back up the EV charging loads, therefore lessening their impact on the network side. In such cases, choices have to be made also about location e.g. deciding whether distributed ESS needs to be placed near the EV chargers, concentrated in selected places in the grid, or using combinations of these solutions. In fact, by combining local (near EV chargers) and grid side ESS, and by adding the time scheduling for coordinating EV charging, an optimized and improved use of the existing grid can be reached.

The Storage4Grid (S4G) project, funded by the European Commission in the H2020-2016-LCE01 area 1 call, starts in this context, and aims at facilitating operation and development of storage technologies within energy systems. In this paper, a scenarios-based requirements elicitation methodology is presented and adopted for use cases generation.

II. BACKGROUND

The S4G project aims to: 1) enable higher efficiency through more self-consumption combined with enhanced charging control of EV and PV's production in existing grids, having as pivotal means the grid and local energy storage

The research work leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 731155 - Storage4Grid project. The sole responsibility of this publication lies with the author(s). The European Union and is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

resources; 2) enable the integration of a bigger share of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) and empower the consumer to choose profitable deals, provided by extensive use of ESS.

A. Vision for Cooperative EV Charging Scenario

To use at the highest degree the power grid, with minimal or no reinforcement, to accommodate as much as possible public and private EV chargers, by combining efficient cooperative charging methods with the support of high ESS penetration.

When consumption increases, network evolution becomes necessary. The traditional solution is based on classic grid reinforcements such as installing bigger transformers and/or new or strengthened lines.

As an alternative, the S4G project starts with the vision of serving the highest possible EV charging services in the current power network without substantial reinforcements.

The project values the synergies between EV charging and storage solutions, in addition to cooperative charging based on correlated charging needs, such as the total EV recharging load is well spread over the day (thus reducing temporary peak loads). Grid-based storage resources need to be used for improving the impact on the grid both in terms of power line reinforcement as well as availability in terms of power delivery capacity close to the charging stations, thus allowing grid acceptance and higher penetration of EV.

The EV vision will be evaluated considering two scenarios: 1) for the current grid situation and 2) in presence of a high penetration of EV charging stations. A scaling of existing EV related process is considered to simulate the congestion inside the grid network.

B. Vision for the Storage Coordination Scenario

To use at the highest degree the power grid, with minimal or no reinforcement, to accommodate the integration of highest RES production and to cover up to 100% of local consumption by using storage coordination of combined ESS at end-user and grid level.

This scenario aligns with the fact that in the medium- to long-term future the grid needs to be able to support highest renewable energy generation without reaching network constraints as foreseen by the Energy Union Winter package [1]. To assess the upcoming higher penetration of renewables, simulations based on existing patterns of RES scaling evolution will be performed considering current and existing smart grid conditions. The potential limitations of actual smart grids when dealing with high RES penetration will be faced through simulations of optimized ESS coordination.

The project intends to show improvements in network operation in both today's situations and in the projected simulated future through appropriate coordination of storage systems opportunely located in a designed and balanced way at end-user level, on grid level or as a combination of both.

C. Stimulating uptake of ESS

In the S4G project, a set of interfaces, predictive control algorithms for Distributed Storage System (DSS), an

In this paper, two S4G visions and their corresponding use cases are further presented.

Unbundled Smart Meter (USM), an Energy Router (ER) and a Decision Support Framework (DSF) will be integrated for modelling, simulating and trying to find solutions in the context of the above two visions.

For both visions introduced above, suitable simulation tools such as PowerFactory, Gridlab-d, OpenModelica, etc. need to be assessed and properly combined. It is important to keep a high correspondence between simulations and real conditions to build different and reliable models for ESS, the power system components as well as predictable control algorithms. The scope of such predictable control algorithms is to prioritize and optimize the use of energy storage in order to serve different stakeholders, including prosumers, grid and market.

One of the main components of S4G is the DSF which is a framework used to support analysis of the selected set of grid scenarios, integrating a set of relevant simulation tools. The DSF will provide to different stakeholders various modelling scenarios, planning ESS tools, forecasting and optimizing solutions of ESS. Other components such as USM and ER will be further explained in section D of III. Methodology.

III. Methodology

This section further describes the methodology used for requirements derivation based on the vision scenarios described in Section II as well as the current situation (as-is) in the two S4G test sites outlined in Section III.A and III.B. Section III.C focuses on user- and stakeholder-involvement and the derivation of relevant requirements, whereas the technical concepts used to realize the S4G vision are further described in Section III.D. Then in the last two subsections use cases generated are solved by exploring S4G's technical approach.

A. Test site in Bolzano: as-is

The *Cooperative EV Charging Scenario* will be set up in Bolzano and operated by EDYNA/ALPERIA. Currently, approximately 250 EVs are active in the area, using a charging network of 19 slow charging station (average power absorbed during charging: 22 kW AC) and two fast charging stations (45 kW DC). The current EV charging infrastructure is monitored and controlled in real-time by EDYNA/ALPERIA through a dedicated SCADA system.

This test site features two pilots: a residential case and a commercial case, as depicted in Fig. 1. For the residential case EDYNA/ALPERIA will use as test site a single-family house in a rural village close to Bolzano. It is already provided with a rooftop PV installation (9,6 kW) and with a residential charging station. Additionally, the house will be equipped with a residential ESS. An USM and a dedicated local Graphical User Interface (GUI) will be integrated into the ESS. From the planning point of view, in this case, the S4G DSF will be employed to support the design and sizing of local energy storage system and its impact on the cost, manageability and environmental sustainability of the EV charging process, both from the private users' and the local Distribution System Operator (DSO)'s point of view.

The commercial case will be tested in the fleet park of EDYNA in the city of Bolzano which is already provided with a rooftop PV installation (49,8 kW). Several parking places of the underground area will be equipped with Charging Units (CU) for EVs.

Fig. 1 Test site in Bolzano

S4G will deploy modified *smart charge boxes* in each of the charging points to enable fine-grained monitoring and control of the charging process. The test site will be completed by installing a substation level ESS compliant with S4G interfaces and models. The S4G DSF will be employed in this scenario to study optimal sizing and design, suggesting the best control strategies of the ESS.

B. Test site in Fur island: as-is

The *Storage Coordination Scenario* will be addressed through the deployment in the Fur test site and it will be led by the partner ENIIG. The island of Fur is located in the Northern part of Denmark in a fjord.

This test site (see Fig. 2) features 5 residential houses which are already provided with 4.2 kWh Li-ion batteries paired with PV installations of diverse sizes (ranging from 3 to 6 kW sizes). The houses have an energy consumption of 4.5-6.3 MWh/year, their self-supply with PV and ESS installed ranges from 20-50%. The residents are both families and couples.

Fig. 2. Storage coordination

The selected houses will be provided with an USM each, integrated with the residential ESS and a dedicated local GUI. The project will investigate whether it is feasible to install batteries at substation-level. If so, a substation-level ESS will be deployed on-site.

It has to be observed that no energy management system (SCADA or alike) is currently available in the described section of the Low Voltage (LV) grid.

C. Scenario-based requirements engineering

S4G uses a scenario-based requirements engineering process that combines both, user-centered design (UCD) [2] as well as technical aspects and conformances. Hereby, it is important to I) involve users and stakeholders using the UCD framework to raise their acceptance towards collaborative energy consumption and encourage them to actively participate in forming future solutions and II) be conformant to already existent standards such as the IEC 62259-2-2015 [3] standard and the mandate SG-CG/M490/E:2012-12 [4].

The requirements engineering process used in S4G can be described as follows: Vision scenarios and as-is descriptions of the test sites deliver a first input for use case creation. Use cases are described in a format that will be conformant to [3] and [4]. Use cases are developed in close collaboration with the responsible persons of the different test sites and are structured in several levels of detail [4]:

- a) High Level Use Case (HLUC): It describes a general requirement, idea or concept independently from a specific technical realization like an architectural solution. In S4G, HLUCs are written from a user perspective to emphasize user needs, goals and issues.
- b) Primary Use Case (PUC): It describes in detail the functionality of (a part of) a business process.
- c) Secondary Use Case (SUC): It is an elementary use case which may be used by several other primary use cases.
- d) Scenarios: It is a possible sequence of interactions.

This structure will be used to organize the identified use cases for S4G based on UCD and technical analysis. The developed use cases will act as an initial source for both, technical and user requirements. Use cases and requirements will be refined and updated continuously throughout the project.

D. Overview of the technology used in S4G

The S4G vision is to provide energy utilities, DSOs and end-users with new tools for optimal grid planning, use, evaluation and comparison of different energy storage technologies. S4G pre-designs new storage control models and interfaces built upon existing standards and suitable to support scalable and cost-efficient coordination of heterogeneous ESS.

S4G will deliver a set of components, as listed below.

1) DSF

The DSF is a set of simulation tools to support analysis of the selected set of grid scenarios.

The DSF will provide different stakeholders including e.g. DSOs, EV service companies, residential and commercial

users, with the possibility to evaluate in advance the feasibility and potential impact of ESS respectively on grid operations, charging costs, self-consumption, etc.

The DSF will also provide the ability to model scenarios characterized by high penetration of EV, also in situations where many charging stations are concentrated in a specific section of the grid, thus requiring the definition of cooperative strategies combining EV Demand Response (DR) and storage control. To achieve more realistic simulation at a lower effort, the DSF will include support for seamlessly importing static, historic and real-time information from the SCADA infrastructure and other tools such as Geographic Information System (GIS).

2) Distributed control methodologies for ESS

The S4G predictive control algorithms are one of the components needed to adapt distribution grid management operations to the scenarios addressed by S4G. They aim at prioritizing and optimizing the use of energy storage capacity in contexts where energy storage units are distributed at end-user premises and at substation level. They also address cooperative charging strategies in the presence of EVs.

3) Unbundled Smart Meter

Unbundled Smart Meter (USM) extends existing AMI standards in open fashion to allow local “plug-in” integration of interfaces providing information about energy storage control, EV charging and local user interfaces to enable interaction with users.

4) ER

The ER is a multi-directional power electronic interface with the following ports: AC port for grid connection; AC port for home AC grid; DC port for home DC grid; DC port for energy storage; DC port for PV panel connection. Among others, the basic functions of the ER involve: Energy flow control and smart energy management; Protection (limiting of fault currents, over voltages, etc.); DR services to grid and user; Communication (grid, unbundled smart meter, DSF, etc.); Improvement of power quality (phase/load balancing, voltage level, harmonics, etc.).

E. Use cases and the S4G approach in Cooperative EV Charging

The HLUC-1 considers that the energy grid in the city of Bolzano is characterized by growing shares of intermittent power generation from RES while facing increasing diffusion of EVs. Such scenario creates new challenges for efficient management and grid stability. One promising solution is to use ESS with the S4G application system. Three PUCs are generated:

1) Residential prosumer with storage - HLUC-1-PUC-1

a) Use case

A prosumer has a rooftop PV and EVs. During the day, the PV usually produces more energy than the household consumes. On the other hand, in order to charge the EVs the household’s energy demand rises during the night.

b) S4G approach

The traditional way would be to upgrade the point of delivery (POD) to cover for the night demand. On the contrary, when choosing to adopt the S4G vision, a better exploitation of the energy produced by the PV is supported. Instead of upgrading the POD, a local ESS is preferred with the assistance of DSF.

Fig. 3. HLUC-1-PUC-1 – Residential prosumer with storage

A Unified Modeling Language (UML) diagram with a variety of stakeholders is shown in Fig. 3.

The S4G DSF receives the task to coordinate the charging of two EVs in a way which allows maximum charging by keeping a given maximal power at POD. One case is that the DSF coordinates the production, energy storage and EV charging with respect to load profiles and constraints. The DSF reports the DSO about how well all tasks have been achieved. Alternatively, the DSF cannot find a solution to fulfil all needs and constraints. The DSF may also give advices about the usage of other consumption loads to improve the goal coverage while respecting constraints.

2) Cooperative charging in the parking lot of a commercial test site - HLUC-1-PUC-2

a) Use case

In Bolzano, a commercial test site with a rooftop PV installation plans to provide itself with a fleet of EVs. The owner aims to equip the parking lot with several charging stations which will use the energy produced by the PV installation.

b) S4G approach

The USMs inform the S4G DSF about production and total consumption at the EDYNA/ALPERIA test site. The DSF receives the task to coordinate the various EV charging in the parking place. One case is to coordinate it in a way which maximizes the charging services while considering PV production, local and grid energy storage status and network constraints set by the DSO. The DSF reports to the DSO about how well all tasks have been achieved. Alternatively, the DSF

reports that it cannot find a solution to serve all needs and constraints. Otherwise, S4G DSF gives advices on how to schedule EV charging so that constraints are met (Fig. 4).

3) *Simulation of high penetration of EVs and of prosumers with storage and residential EV charging - HLUC-1-PUC-3*

a) *Use case*

Fig. 4. HLUC-1-PUC-2 - Cooperative charging in the parking lot of a commercial test site

This use case aims to evaluate through simulation the maximum number of EV charging stations and residential charging points that can be handled with the existing network, with storage and cooperative charging, without needing to reinforce the grid. While the first two use cases depict existing situations, this one evaluates a future scenario, where a massive diffusion of EVs is likely to threaten the stability of the grid and the growing load may be especially difficult to handle. The simulation will be done inside DSF, by using scaling factors to simulate high EV penetration and charging services.

b) *S4G approach*

The DSO selects specific places for the EV charging; a simplified repartition of EV chargers can be made by aggregating some of the points in a single network point. The DSF coordinates the production, storage and EV charging till the grid limitation, whereas assuring that constraints are met. The DSF reports about how well all tasks have been achieved. It is also able to conclude that there is no solution that meets all needs and constraints. By using scaling factors, the S4G DSF can show the limit of EV charging stations in existing (or slightly enforced) network while meeting constraints. A new cooperative algorithm applicable at the scaled situation might increase the penetration of EV chargers in the existing network.

F. *Use cases and the S4G approach in Storage coordination*

Decentralized production in the LV grid in the form of PV and small wind generators gives a new energy flow. With high production and low consumption, the energy will flow from the low voltage grid towards the higher voltage levels which

causes grid loss. The increasing use of RES aggravates problems caused by unstable voltage levels in the grid. In grid planning, the transformers and the tap changers are usually designed per the voltage drops in the cables related to the consumption, but with decentralized production the grid now experiences two situations. One is during high production and low consumption, the voltage rises, the other is during high consumption and low production, the voltage drops.

This leads to the necessity to trim the transformers in different settings during different situations. In low voltage areas, there is no monitoring and no remote control, thereby trimming is a manual task as one must go to the transformer in person.

The added amount of consumption of electric energy will naturally give an added stress on the grid as this is planned per the historical electricity consumption. With the added focus on electric vehicles as well as electric heating, the amount of consumed energy will experience a sudden rise for which the grid is not designed. This will ultimately amount to lower voltage in the grid, less reliable supply of electricity and more grid losses.

Same situation but reversed will be present when Distributed Energy Resources (DER) are producing more than the consumption is in the local grid and a rise in voltage will occur which was not intended and will lead to grid losses and low quality electricity for the consumer, besides lower prices on selling former stored energy.

Instead of installing bigger cables and transformers, an alternative way is suggested by the S4G vision. The solution is to install remote controlled storage in the grid might in one or the other way help avoiding these situations and thereby avoid grid strengthening.

1) *Traditional grid strengthening simulation - HLUC-2-PUC-1*

a) *Use case*

The grid planner wants to strength the grid capacity by considering installing transformers and cables.

Fig. 5. HLUC-2-PUC-1 – Traditional grid strengthening simulation

The expectations of DSO, ENIIG, are to gain less voltage issues and lower grid losses. Furthermore, there are other downsides for this option, such as power loss caused by the electricity cables or environmental damage due to the cable production or track laying itself. This option determines the economic and technical baseline for benchmarking as it's the traditional way to overcome congestion problems in DSO grids.

To find the best option for all, customers, the environment and the DSO, the grid planner will run the simulations of the baseline, the well-known grid strengthening.

b) S4G approach

By using S4G DSF, firstly strategic grid planner specifies the options used for traditional grid strengthening, network topology which should be involved in the simulation, and loads historical data (consumption, production, storage) from data storage, then specifies tap changer settings, planning scheme and/or guidelines used for traditional grid strengthening or create new operation demands. During simulation phase, S4G DSF simulates grid situation (or new normal coupling) and shows results which helps strategic grid planner analyses expected future changes in the grid (see Fig. 5).

2) Simulation of private households investing in residential storage - HLUC-2-PUC-2

a) Use case

The grid planner is interested in what happens if more private households are investing in residential storage to increase their self-sufficiency. Current issue is that these prosumers do not report the installation to ENIIG and ENIIG has no access or knowledge about these installations. The Battery Management Systems (BMS) for these storages are autonomous and run independent of the grid, which affects the energy flow in uncontrolled way. The grid planner needs to simulate the impact on the grid stability without further control mechanisms.

b) S4G approach

At household level, a battery needs to be installed to optimize use of energy from production. By launching S4G DSF, strategic grid planner specifies the options used for traditional grid strengthening, network topology which should be involved in the simulation and loads historical data (consumption, production, energy storage) from data storage and tap changer settings. Then strategic grid planner specifies planning scheme and/or guidelines used for traditional grid strengthening. During simulation process, S4G DSF simulates grid situation and display results. Strategic grid planner analyses expected future changes in the grid. Finally, it is possible to buy and sell stored energy to the grid following spot prices. Aggregators may be introduced.

3) DSO investing in larger systems at substation level - HLUC-2-PUC-3

a) Use case

The third option for the grid planner to simulate is if he or she can place ESS in the low voltage grid. This situation allows to further investigate on the most suitable positioning and placement of storage in the grid, the correct dimension of the

battery taking consumption and production into account, as well as lifetime and operational cost.

b) S4G approach

By using S4G DSF, strategic grid planner specifies the network topology which should be involved in the simulation, and loads historical data (consumption, production, storage) from data storage. Then strategic grid planner specifies set-point behaviour. During simulation process, S4G DSF simulates grid situation and displays results. Strategic grid planner analyses the results with a technical and economical perspective besides expected future changes in the grid. DSF scales up the situation (consumption, production, storage) to simulate on a reduced network topology a high penetration of RES (up to 100%).

4) Deploying and enforcing distributed controllable storage at various levels - HLUC-2-PUC-4

a) Use case

The fourth option for the grid planner is the simulation of a cooperation between prosumers with unknown private ESS and ESS owned by ENIIG.

b) S4G approach

Using the same starting phase of inputs as the solution for HLUC-2-PUC-3, strategic Grid Planner specifies location of battery in grid topology, and S4G DSF displays results, or DSF receives the availability of the storage device from each storage resource, scales up the situation (consumption, production, storage) to simulate on a reduced network topology a high penetration of RES (up to 100%) and tries to address network constraints by simulating set-point to BMS. S4G can simulate impact or sending set-point to aggregators and aggregators sending set-point to BMS. Strategic grid planner analyses the results with a technical and economical perspective besides expected future changes in the grid.

IV. Conclusions

Storage4Grid is a joint effort between seven EU partners: three research centres (ISMB, Fraunhofer FIT, UNINOVA), one university (UPB), two utilities (Eniig Forsyning A/S and Edyna, Alperia Group) and one Battery Management Systems (BMS) provider (Lithium Balance A/S). Storage4Grid started in December 2016 and will run for 36 months. Results will be disseminated through the Storage4Grid project website [5].

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